

The Characteristics of Speech Art in Increasing the Effectiveness of Spiritual and Educational Events

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Annotation:

This article examines issues related to improving the effectiveness of using the art of oratory in spiritual and educational work, speech activity, the teaching of speech, its significance and tasks, and the requirements for speech skills in the processes of spirituality and enlightenment.

Keywords: spirituality, enlightenment, word, spiritual and educational work, oratory, rhetoric, speech culture, communication styles, the mechanism of preparation for the art of oratory.

In any period, the strength and support of a country are measured by the achievements of the country's youth in scientific fields, the development of sports and art, the systematization of production and industry, ensuring economic stability, and the consistent promotion of spiritual and educational activities. Therefore, it should be noted that spirituality is an integral characteristic of a person and all humanity, and the education of young people is a means of enriching their consciousness and thinking. According to the definition of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev,... "Spirituality is a combination of mutual trust, respect and attention between people, noble aspirations for the joint construction of the future of the people and the state, exemplary qualities." In other words, spirituality is the foundation that determines the content and quality of all political and social relations in society"¹. The effective and successful results of economic and political reforms, modernization, and innovation processes implemented in Uzbekistan today, as well as the adaptation of the education system to the demands of the modern

¹ Sh.M.Mirziyoev. Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasi. – T: O'zbekiston, 2021. B.267.

world, are inextricably linked to the development of the spiritual sphere. In particular, as we face such an important task as raising our youth as a comprehensively developed, educated and capable generation, it is necessary to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational events, properly organize them, meaningfully spend the free time of young people and ensure their active participation in these events. So, what can spiritual and educational events give young people? Or let's first look for an answer to the question: what is the main purpose of holding such events? It is known that after Uzbekistan gained independence, the problem of spirituality became one of the main issues on the agenda. If we pay attention to the concept of spirituality, we understand that this social phenomenon is a long-standing process that has taken place alongside the history of humanity. We can witness that spiritual and moral issues are reflected in the ideas of ancient religious sources, including Buddhism, Judaism, and Zoroastrianism. The term "spirituality" is based on the Arabic word "meaning." It is known that there is an external and internal world of man. The external world includes his height, appearance, dress, behavior, and so on. His inner world encompasses his purpose in life, his thinking, his dreams, and his feelings. Therefore, it is understood that the inner world of a person in the process of life and its manifestation in existence is spirituality. The ancient Chinese sage Confucius put forward the idea of humanism as the fundamental center of spirituality. Moreover, the spiritual ideas of the ancient Greek thinkers Democritus, Socrates, and Aristotle about the development of society, upbringing, and self-awareness laid the foundation for the formation of human spirituality. Eastern scholars also had a significant influence on the development of spirituality and morality. In particular, the issue of spirituality is emphasized in the works of a number of world-renowned ancestors, such as Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Musa al-Khwarizmi, Ibn Sina, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Ahmad Yugnaki, Abu Rayhan al-Biruni, and Imam al-Bukhari. Jalal ad-Din Rumi, who lived in the 13th century, wrote in his work "Ma'navi Masnavi": "Man differs from other creatures in his thinking and beliefs." The morality and spiritual image of a person's spirituality are manifested in their soul. Spiritual maturity is reflected in the positive qualities of a person² The author of the dissertation makes important remarks on the following. Ibn Sina, a genius of the medical world, said that negative human qualities can be eliminated through moral education.³ In the 20th century, our Jadidists, such as Abdulla Avloni, Abdurauf Fitrat, Abdulla Kadiri, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Ishaqon Ibrat, Cholpon, Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, who care about educating the nation's youth, raising their consciousness and awareness, also paid attention to spiritual and educational, moral qualities in their ideas. This shows that spirituality has always been one of the most pressing issues. Today, more than ever, attention should be paid to the issue of spirituality. Undoubtedly, spiritual and educational events play an invaluable role in promoting our national identity and instilling it in the minds of young people, expanding knowledge about our rich spiritual heritage, the life and work of our ancestors in the past. Today, our country is creating numerous resolutions, legislative acts, and scientific works on issues of spirituality and spiritual education. The work of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, "The Strategy of New Uzbekistan," is considered a programmatic work in the theoretical analysis of issues of spirituality and spiritual education. The fifth part of this work is called "Spiritual Development," and it analyzes the issue of spirituality. The work focuses on the formation of an enlightened society in New Uzbekistan and its factors, ensuring the harmony of national and universal values in the development of society, and other issues related to the sphere of spirituality.⁴ Spiritual and educational events are also one of the important areas of education and upbringing. There are two main objectives in organizing spiritual and educational events: First, to glorify human virtues, study the lives and activities of highly spiritual individuals, and present them as role models. The second is to condemn certain negative

² Ma'naviy masnaviy. 1-jild. 1-kitob. –T.: 1999. –B. 101; 283.

³ Abu ali ibn Sino. Filosofskie traktat. – M: Nauka. 1980. – S. 43.

⁴ Sh.M.Mirziyoyev. Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasi. – T: O'zbekiston, 2021. B.267.

vices, encourage their elimination, and promote the formation of positive qualities. In such events, it is crucial to showcase the life paths of our great ancestors, their legacy, and our progressive contemporaries who are currently working effectively in their respective fields in our country. To properly and systematically organize such events, it is advisable for a person to possess knowledge of the art of public speaking and verbal techniques. Naturally, every word spoken during the event captures the listeners' attention. It is imperative that the event organizer or any intellectual speaking on stage not only limit themselves to thoughts about the past, but also possess the ability to convey their ideas to the participants in the most impactful, understandable, and fluent manner, relying on accurate information about current reforms, opportunities created in all areas, and modern technologies. A thorough analysis of each sentence uttered during spiritual and educational events and the revelation of the topic's consistent essence, without losing the sequence of ideas, has a special significance. Only then will spiritual and educational events truly resonate with people's hearts and minds. Spiritual activities, by their nature, have a pedagogical foundation, as pedagogy primarily governs educational processes. Positive influence on people, exemplary behavior, spiritual nourishment, and all other similar concepts reveal the essence of these events. One of the famous Russian film directors, N. Danchenko, expresses his opinion on the effective organization of events and highlights three distinct qualities of a director. He emphasizes the need to possess the characteristics of a "director-mirror, director-teacher, and director-organizer." As a director-mirror, one should be able to see the true essence of everything, work on oneself, and develop speech by self-reflection. A director-teacher must have mastered pedagogical ethics, aesthetic taste, and ethical rules, understanding the essence of each word to be spoken at the event and how it will affect people. As a director-organizer, it is advisable that all processes of the spiritual and educational event be managed by a responsible person in an organizational capacity. Applying these qualities in organizing spiritual and educational events serves to enhance the event's impact. Only when the speaker's speech is perfect in all respects can harmony between education and upbringing be achieved, increasing the event's effectiveness and making its impact more noticeable. Therefore, developing public speaking skills is particularly important for conducting any spiritual and educational event. It can be said that a speech that is engaging and pleasant, providing both content and enjoyment to the listener, also determines a person's standing in society. It can be said that a speech that is attractive and pleasant, gives content and pleasure to the listener, also determines a person's level in society.

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